

CONSIDERATION OF ADHESIVE JOINTS FOR A MULTI-MATERIAL TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Competition and governmental regulations regarding CO₂ emissions are forcing the automotive industry to reduce component weights and costs. To achieve these goals, the use of lightweight design and composite materials has increased significantly in the last couple of years. However, the broad use of those materials is still being prevented by high material and production costs. On the contrary, hybrid parts seem particularly promising as they offer a high potential of weight reduction with simultaneously low costs. The advantage of hybrid structures, compared to single material parts, results from the targeted use of each material. For casting parts, the mix of iron and a (fiber reinforced) plastic is a possible combination. Topology optimization is already widely used in the automotive industry to design casting parts. With most commercial optimization approaches using just one material, there is interest for an optimizer which could handle hybrid structures. Also, existing multi-material topology optimization approaches do not focus on the joining of the different materials. This could result in significant differences between the optimized and the final design. Besides other joining techniques like interlocking structures, an adhesive joint is particularly suited for a material combination like steel and plastic. The main challenge lies in integrating the design of the adhesive joining in the optimization process. The first step is to model the adhesive layer in the numerical analysis. Two possible approaches using special purpose finite elements are described in this paper. Furthermore, a comparison of topology optimization results shows the influence of the adhesive modeling. Finally, a mechanical stress-based approach to optimize the geometry of an adhesive joint as part of the topology optimization process is illustrated.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, topology optimization is already widely used in the industry to design casting parts in an early stage of the development process. As only a limited number of restrictions on the design of the part are made, new lightweight structures can evolve. Therefore, this optimization technique is particularly interesting for multi-material parts, for which design rules are not yet fully established.

Over the past two decades different topology optimization approaches have been proposed, but only few of them can be used for multi-material problems. One popular topology optimization approach is the SIMP (Solid Isotropic Microstructure with Penalization) method developed by Bendsoe [1]. An

extension to this approach for a multi-material challenge is the RMMI (Recursive Multiphase Materials Interpolation) scheme [2]. Two other multi-material interpolation schemes were presented by Hvejsel and Lund, where one is also based on SIMP while the other one is based on the RAMP (Rational Approximation of Material Properties) scheme [3]. A topology optimization solver for multi-material challenges based on the famous 99-line MATLAB code by Sigmund [4, 5] was developed by Tavakoli and Mohseni [6]. Most recently, advances were made in the development of multi-material topology optimization methods adapting a multi-phase level-set model [7-9]. A fundamentally different approach based on evolutionary algorithms was used by Hiller and Lipson for the topology optimization of three-dimensional multi-material structures [10].

2 MULTI-MATERIAL TOPOLOGY OPTIMIZATION

The Multi-Material Topology Optimization is an extension of a new approach for topology optimization [11-14]. The main target is to find a cost- and weight-efficient solution. With this approach, linear and nonlinear FEA as well as manufacturing requirements can be covered. The optimization mechanism shown in figure 1 is similar to a controller loop. At first, a step size is calculated which determines the number of elements that are going to be changed in this loop. Afterwards, the structure of the part is modified depending on this value. In a next step, special elements are added to model the cohesive interface between the two materials. A more detailed description of how these elements are added is given in the following section. Subsequently, the mesh is written into a FEA input deck for the mechanical simulation. The results of this simulation are returned to the optimizer and another optimization loop is started.

Figure 1: Flow chart of the Multi-Material Topology Optimization Method

To help avoid challenges in the nonlinear FEA a binary material definition is used. This definition is extended for the multi-material optimization. Every element of the FE mesh can now have the states nonexistent, material one or material two. A biological growth rule similar to the SKO (Soft Kill Option) or BESO (Bi-Directional Evolutionary Structural Optimization) method changes the states of the elements depending on the mechanical stress values in these elements [15, 16]. Figure 2 shows the three implemented mechanisms.

Figure 2: The three mechanism: a) converting, b) adding, and c) removing elements

The first mechanism changes the material of single elements to modify the ratio of both materials. As every material has specific lightweight properties, each one is suitable for different load situations. During the optimization process the material with the ideal properties is preferred. The second mechanism is adding elements to reduce demanded areas by setting the neighboring element states to the material of the highly demanded element. If the neighboring material already has a higher Young's modulus, the material is not changed. Afterwards, the third mechanism removes low demanded elements of the lower density material, or changes the material for elements of the higher density material. This mechanism is used to reduce the weight of the structure.

The amount of elements that should be converted, added, or removed, is calculated in an extended step size controller. Every rate is calculated for both materials and so, both materials are changed independently to help avoid unwanted influences and ensure the wanted material distribution. For the calculation, several parameters are evaluated. At first a basic rate is determined which is similar to the single material optimization. A low constraint allows the removal of many elements and only few elements have to be added. When the constraint rises, the weight reduction is slower and more elements are added to help avoid hotspots. With the basic rate, the material specific rates are calculated with a group of fuzzy systems. Input parameters for this systems are shown in figure 3.

Figure 3: Input and output parameter of the fuzzy systems

The mechanism checks the current situation of the optimization and the material combination. It chooses the best material for this situation and privileges it. This material is reduced less as well as added and converted more than the other material. In this way an ideal material distribution and ratio can be achieved.

In a single material topology optimization the use of less material directly means less cost. For a multi-material optimization, the lightest design often is not the most cost-efficient solution, as each material has different costs per mass. Therefore, the user can define a cost factor for both materials which influences the usage of each material during the optimization process.

3 MODELING OF THE ADHESIVE LAYER

Existing multi-material topology optimization approaches typically do not take into consideration the interface between the different materials [17]. However, depending on the type of joint, significantly different structures could be necessary in the final design when compared to the optimization result. Furthermore, a high difference in the stiffness of the materials leads to high strain differences at the joint. In the original modelling all neighboring elements are sharing nodes. As a result the joint is represented in the FE model as an ideal connection between both materials and the transmission of forces is not modeled realistically at the interface. Therefore, one step to get an optimization result closer to an industrially producible design is to integrate the joint modeling into the optimization process.

One widely used type of joint for hybrid parts is the adhesive bond. Two different approaches to model an adhesive joint in the topology optimization process will be shown in this section. As Abaqus is used for the simulation examples in this paper, the following modeling approaches are based on the available element types in Abaqus, but could be used for other FE solvers offering cohesive elements as well (but different restrictions may apply).

To model an adhesive joint, usually, cohesive elements are used. Abaqus offers three different types of cohesive elements, which differ in the mechanical constitutive response model. The first type, the continuum-based modeling, directly uses the macroscopic properties of the adhesive material and is appropriate for adhesives with a finite thickness. The traction-separation-based modeling, as the second type, can be used for very thin adhesive layers. The constitutive response is directly defined in terms of traction versus separation (see figure 4) with the macroscopic properties of the material not being directly relevant. The third type of cohesive element may be used to model gaskets or laterally unconstrained adhesive patches. [18]

Figure 4: Traction-separation law (cf. [18])

To model an adhesive joint in the topology optimization process, the continuum-based as well as the traction-separation-based modeling seem suited. For the optimization of the adhesive bonds (see section 5), we are interested in the normal mechanical stress in the thickness direction and the two shear mechanical stress values in plane of the adhesive layer. Preliminary examinations have shown that for the initial loading of the adhesive layer, both models deliver the same values for all three demanded components, as the behavior of the material in this phase can be described as linear elastic. Therefore, both element types are taken into consideration.

To model the adhesive joints in the topology optimization process, the interfaces must firstly be identified. Therefore, a routine searches for contact surfaces between two elements of different material. The contact surface is defined by the four shared nodes of both elements (3D). These nodes are duplicated and the resulting nodes are assigned to one of the elements. Thereby, the two elements are separated. The next step is to add a cohesive element using the four original and the four new nodes. The thickness direction of the cohesive element is defined by the normal vector of the contact surface.

3.1 Continuum-based modeling

As the continuum-based modeling requires a geometric thickness of the element, the FE mesh must be modified at the joint. The element nodes connected to the cohesive element are displaced by half the thickness of the adhesive layer in respectively counter the thickness direction, as shown in figure 5a and 5c. A single element can have multiple contact surfaces requiring a cohesive element and a node may be in need of being displaced in up to all three coordinate directions (3D). As a result, the elements connected by the cohesive element are distorted. The maximum thickness of the adhesive layer is therefore limited to a fraction of the voxel element edge length, as excessive distortion of elements should be avoided. For a values exceeding the maximum thickness, a thickness value can be specified in the element properties.

3.2 Traction-Separation-based modeling

Using the traction-separation-based modeling, the thickness of the adhesive layer is always specified in the properties of the cohesive element and is typically different from the geometric thickness. Furthermore, the cohesive element can have a geometric thickness equal to zero. This allows a modeling

of the adhesive bonds without any mesh distortion (see figure 5b and 5d) as the coincident doubled nodes can be used without be displaced.

Figure 5: Mesh modification for cohesive elements (*green*)

4 COMPARISON OF OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

To compare the optimization results, a simple academic structure, as shown in figure 6, will be examined. The structure is a square plate with a size of 100 mm by 100 mm and a thickness of 7 mm. The FE model is discretized by voxel elements with an edge length of 1 mm, resulting in a total number of 70,000 elements. The plate is fixed in rotation and translation on the top left corner. The two single point loads are applied on the bottom right corner, for which two different loadcases are distinguished. The corners, in which the boundaries and loads are applied, are non-design areas. Those areas remain unchanged during the optimization process (blue areas in figure 6). The rest of the structure is the design area (grey area in figure 6), which can be modified by the optimizer. At the beginning of the optimization, the design space is filled with the stiffer material, in this example steel with a Young's modulus of $E = 210,000 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and a density of $\rho = 7850 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The second material is a plastic with a lower Young's modulus of $E = 6,500 \text{ N/mm}^2$ and a lower density of $\rho = 1560 \text{ kg/m}^3$. The Poisson's ratio for both materials is $\nu = 0.3$. The start, minimum, and maximum basic rate as well as other optimization parameters and constraints are equal for all four optimization calculations. For the multi-material optimization with the modeling of adhesive joints, the thickness of the adhesive layer is set to 0.2 mm and the same material data is used as for the plastic.

Figure 6: Academic example: square plate (boundary and loads)

The maximum mechanical stress in the steel elements is limited to 400 N/mm^2 , whereas the limit for the plastic elements is set to 100 N/mm^2 . Moreover, the deflection of the whole structure is limited to 1 mm at the load application point to obtain structures with a similar stiffness. The number of optimization iterations is set to 100 loops. The results of all four optimization calculations are shown in table 1.

Comparing the single and the multi-material optimization results, both structures are considerably different in weight according to expectations. As for both structures an outer frame of steel elements bearing the load is formed. To support this outer frame, the single material optimization result uses very few struts of steel, while the multi material result uses more and wider struts of plastic. Thereby, the amount of steel is lowered by 36 %. Even with the broad use of plastic and the overall more filled design space, the multi-material result is about 27 % lighter as the plastic only has about one fifth of the density of steel.

By modeling the adhesive joint, the overall stiffness of the structure is lowered and more material must be used to achieve the same maximum deflection. This explains why the multi-material result with the continuum-based adhesive modeling is about 4 % heavier than the multi-material structure without any interface modeling. Comparing both structures, a more extensive use of plastic is noticeable (about 7.5 % more plastic elements) as well as a slightly higher fraction of steel.

The multi-material optimization result using the traction-separation based modeling is about 5 % heavier than the result without any interface modeling. It is also slightly heavier than the result using the continuum-based modeling as more steel elements are used. The volume fraction of the plastic is equal for both types of modeling. However, the plastic structure supporting the outer steel frame is more compact and rather resembles a planar structure than a structure of struts. Furthermore, the separation of both materials is cleaner and there are significantly less isolated plastic elements on the steel structure. The difference between both modeling types can partially be explained by the distortion of the elements at the joint when using the continuum-based modeling.

Single material	Multi-material without adhesive joint	Multi-material with adhesive joint (continuum-based)	Multi-material with adhesive joint (traction-sep.-based)
Volume fractions: 15.3 % steel 0.0 % plastic	Volume fractions: 9.8 % steel 6.7 % plastic	Volume fractions: 10.2 % steel 7.2 % plastic	Volume fractions: 10.3 % steel 7.2 % plastic
-	-	Area of cohesive layer: 1374 mm ²	Area of cohesive layer: 996 mm ²
Weight: 84.2 g	Weight: 61.3 g	Weight: 63.7 g	Weight: 64.6 g

Table 1: Optimization results – Volume fractions & weight

5 OPTIMIZATION OF THE ADHESIVE JOINT

The advantage of using cohesive elements in contrast to just defining a cohesive interaction between the surfaces of both element is that the mechanical stress in the adhesive material is known and the durability of the joint can be analyzed. In the examples shown in the previous section, the mechanical stress in the adhesive layer was not limited to a maximum value. In reality, the adhesive joint can fail

when a maximum normal or shear mechanical stress is exceeded. To prevent this failure, all joints should be evaluated and, if necessary, modified to lower the mechanical stress at this joint.

To evaluate the mean mechanical stress in a single joint, connecting cohesive elements are grouped, with each group representing one cohering interface, and the average mechanical stress of all elements in that group is calculated. Furthermore, the highest mechanical stress values are normally to be found at the edge of the joint, especially for multi-material structures. If a preassigned maximum mechanical stress value is exceeded, the joint may need to be modified in this area.

A first approach for this modification is shown for a 2D structure in figure 7. The first step is to check the status of the two direct neighbor elements (marked with the letter 'N' in figure 7). If one or both elements have the state nonexistent, these elements are added in the next step. The contact surface of the bond is thereby increased and the mean mechanical stress in the bond is lowered. A further third step could add additional elements, increasing the contact surface even more. Also, by widening the cross-section of the structure in direction to joint, the mechanical stress values in the edges of the joint are lowered and thereby the overall mechanical stress distribution is improved. This step can be repeated several times, depending on the violation of the maximum mechanical stress in the original design.

Figure 7: Optimization approach for the adhesive joints

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented a new topology optimization approach for multi-material structures. Furthermore, two solutions to integrate the modeling of adhesive joints in the optimization process were described. The influence of the adhesive joint modeling on the topology optimization was shown in a comparison of optimization results. Thereby, a difference between the two modeling types became identifiable. It still needs to be determined which type of modeling leads to a more realistic representation of the adhesive joints and if a local refinement of the mesh is necessary for the cohesive elements. This requires a comparison of FEM calculations and experimental data.

When a realistic representation of the adhesive joints is established, the demanded components in the adhesive layer can be used to optimize the joints. A first idea for a joint optimization as part of the topology optimization has already been presented in this paper. The optimization of the joints in combination with the integration of additional manufacturing restrictions for multi-material parts has a valuable potential of achieving realistic and manufacturable designs with the topology optimization approach.

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